

JOURNALIST PERSONNEL TRAINING AS A SCIENTIFIC- PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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I.A. Fateeva defines the journalism education system as "studying stable forms of organization and regulation of social life sees it as a direction" and evaluates it as a "social institution" in contrast to the pedagogical encyclopedia's definition of it as "a system of training creative employees of newspapers, magazines, radio broadcasting, and television, as well as editors of mass literature" [1-912]: "Of course, journalism education is a social institution created to carry out objectives and duties with a certain level of social significance. Like any other social institution, journalism education caters to and serves the needs of a certain social group [2-26]."

According to B.N. Lozovsky, journalism education is mostly practiced in universities and is interpreted as a system of personnel training. He produced *Journalism and the Media: A Concise Dictionary*, which provides the following definition:

"System of staff training in universities for the newspaper, television, and radio industries. It is primarily prepared in publicly funded higher education institutions using the state education requirement for the field or specialty of "journalism". The standard outlines the requirements for a graduate and presupposes mastery of three cycles of sciences: natural and applied mathematics, humanities and socioeconomics, and professional. The institutional divisions of universities are faculties, departments, and departments that train specialists in the mass media [3-71]. From the viewpoints covered here, it is clear that journalism education is broadly explained.

This demonstrates that journalism education is a system for developing highly educated workers with professional knowledge, skills, and qualifications who work in the mass media, i.e a system for developing qualified personnel carried out in higher education institutions in accordance with the state educational standard.

A doctor of philology, professor L.P. Shesterkina highlights journalism education as a system of journalism that ensures the growth and enhancement of the field's human resource capacity [4-21]. The scientist who focused on the process of training journalists in the context of convergence emphasizes that the

universal journalist training program includes the balance of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, and qualifications that meet the requirements of the time [5–11], and that the successful implementation of plans for training and retraining of specialists should be based on a modern material and technical base that meets the requirements of the time.

Researchers have employed the idea of journalism education under several labels. In her PhD dissertation on the theory and history of journalism education, Russian scientist I.A.Fateeva specifically employs the ideas of "journalistic education - professional media education" as mutually synonymous words [2-28].

The professional training of those who hold this profession takes place directly in editorial offices, as noted by pedagogue T.N. Vladimirova, who conducted in-depth research on the system of journalistic professional training. She also demonstrates that this process is primarily related to the acquisition of practical skills and qualifications for journalistic activity [6-31].

Since journalism is a creative activity, it is essential for students in this profession to first express their creativity, then develop their practical and theoretical understanding of journalism, as well as their creativity-related skills and abilities.

The major objective of journalism education, regardless of who the educators are, is to strengthen not only journalists but also journalism itself, according to the interpretation of British academics G. Berger and J. Foot who focused on the role and purpose of journalism education in society. In other words, it is presumable that the quality of journalism education has an impact on the quality of society and its individuals. Education in journalism benefits both the general population and professional journalists. This objective highlights the critical role journalism educators play in advancing media literacy and the interests of the media industry, which has a larger objective of serving the public [7].

Several scientists agree that a variety of characteristics directly affect how a journalist becomes a specialist, including the following: Future journalists are developed as people and professionals outside of the university. The social environment, the appearance of contemporary print and electronic media, which frequently do not represent the best examples of journalistic products, the ethical principles, values, and professional standards of the editorial environment, as well as the requirements that students must meet when

beginning to cooperate in editorial offices, sometimes from the first courses [8-23], are all extremely important.

To put it briefly, foreign experts see the training of journalists as a scientific-pedagogical problem. The training of aspiring journalists, the study of the educational process from the pedagogical point of view, and the training of highly educated journalists all serve to increase the effectiveness of scientific research in this area.

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